

SOLVENCY RATIO AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF LISTED INDUSTRIAL GOODS FIRM IN NIGERIA EXCHANGE GROUP

¹Dr. Obani Chimaobi Desmond, ²Dr. Ozuomba Chidinma Nwamaka, ³Dr. Agu Charles Ikechukwu and ⁴Dr. Ogujiofor Magnus Nkemjika

^{1,3}Department of Accountancy, Caritas University, Amorji Nike, Enugu State, Nigeria.

²Department of Accounting, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, Imo State, Nigeria.

⁴Department of Accounting, Novena University Ogume, Delta State, Nigeria.

Email: obanichimaobi28@gmail.com, chimaobidobani@caritasuni.edu.ng / chidinmaozuomba@gmail.com, chidinma.ozuomba@uaes.edu.ng / savedeby@gmail.com / henrymagng@yahoo.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14002764>

Abstract: The study examined solvency ratio and financial performance of industrial goods firms in Nigeria. Three specific objectives and hypotheses were formulated. The study adopted ex-post facto research design. Cross sectional panel data secondarily sourced from the annual financial reports and accounts of nine (9) listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria, from 2013 to 2023 were analyzed using descriptive statistics, normality graph, hausman specification test, and ordinary least square regression analyses with the aid of E-view 9 at 5% level of significance. The study proxy Solvency using Interest coverage ratio, debt to asset ratio and debt to equity ratio as explanatory variables while financial performance proxy using return on asset as response variable. The findings shown that the coefficient of interest coverage ratio is -0.012 and has a negative relationship with return on asset. The coefficient for Debt to asset ratio is -0.76 and has insignificant relationship with return on asset while the coefficient for debt-to-equity ratio is 0.05 with a positive relationship with return on asset of industrial goods firms in Nigeria. The study concludes that debt to asset ratio is the only significant variable on return on asset of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria Exchange Group. Although interest coverage ratio and debt to equity ratio financial maintain negative and positive coefficients respectively with insignificant effect on the return on asset of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria Exchange Group and recommends that managers of industrial goods firms in Nigeria should proficiently strategize the interest coverage ratio of the firms, in a manner that the Operational efficiency of the firm takes comparative advantage over the exposure of investment risk.

Keywords: Solvency Ratio, Financial Performance, Industrial Goods Firms, Debt-to-Asset Ratio, Return on Assets

INTRODUCTION

The main objective of any company is to maximize its profit. A company that does not make profit cannot survive in business for a long time. In other words, effective and effective and efficient management to obtain profitability are very important for company's survival. Maximizing shareholders wealth is only possible if the company makes adequate profit to be distributed out as dividends. One of the management's tasks is to conduct financial management which will assure that managers will make decisions that will increase shareholders' wealth. Therefore, proper planning must be done to mitigate the risks that may affect the profits or prevent the achievement of this goal. Companies focus on profitability because it plays a critical role in evaluating the current financial health and stability of a company and achieving high performance and growth in the future. Profitability requires that income derived from the company's business activities exceeds the company's expense.

Profitability depends on the working capital because an inefficient working capital management might lead to lack of profitability and tend to the financial crisis. Every business requires working capital for its survival. Working capital is essential for continuous business operations. A sufficient level of cash is also inevitable to be able to cope with the short and long-term debt, the basic purpose of solvency.

Solvency refers to a company's ability to fulfill its obligations. Assessment of a company's ability to pay its obligations such as interest and principal payments generally includes analysis of the components of its financial structure. Solvency ratios provide information regarding the relative amount of debt in the company's capital structure and adequacy of earnings and cash flow to cover interest assets. Solvency impacts a company's ability to obtain loan, financing, investment capital, and the indication of a company's current and long-term financial health and stability as determined by assets ratio to liability. Solvency management is aim to ensure capital sufficiency for an organization, control the degree of indebtedness through the requirement of minimum indicator threshold and sustain a proper mix between equity and debt funding in the long-run.

Although firm's solvency plays an important role in firm's financial performance, but inefficient and ineffective utilization of debt-equity mix results in sub-optimal level of capital structure portrays a significant challenge to firm's management. Optimal debt structure refers to the level which minimizes the cost of Company's capital and maximizes the performance of the firm (Oboro & Samuel, 2021). The use of debt finance offers an opportunity to the firm to increase the scale of its operations and consequently increase its performance over time. However, debt finance has such effects in performance, if the return on the assets is greater than the cost of debt (Aziz & Abbas, 2019). Apart from investment decision, firm solvency has become one of the important financial decisions of business organization because of its long-term financial impact on firm's operations with specific reference to the maximization of shareholders wealth and firm value (Aziz & Abbas, 2019).

Industrial goods sector is a vital driver of the Nigerian economy, therefore its importance on the financial sustainability of industrial goods firms cannot be overemphasized. However, lack of effective solvency management and cash-flow challenges among Nigerian industrial firms would leave them on the brink of collapse. Financial leverage as a component of solvency management plays a key role in determining financial

sustainability. The use of debt promotes business, increase revenues and profitability. Nevertheless, non-payment of these debt due to firms' insolvency possess challenges with consequences which are not limited to decline in credit rating, termination of banking and other credit extension services, withdrawal of all support and patronage from suppliers and customers, sales of the company's assets to pay off its creditors, impairment in future investment and business relationship as well as compulsory liquidation of the firm.

The question of what constitutes an optimal solvency ratio remains unanswered and has been one of the most controversial issues in the finance circles (Okpala & Omaliko, 2010). Therefore, there is not yet a generally accepted firm solvency ratio on the performance of industrial goods firms in Nigeria with the evidence from previous research works of, Akaji, Nwadiolor & Agubata, 2021, Jensen & Meckling, 1984, etc. This serves as a need for this study, effect of solvency ratio on the financial performance of industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

Therefore, based on the above backdrop, the study investigates the effect of solvency ratio on the financial performance of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

Solvency Ratio

A company can be valued by its solvability when the company has sufficient asset to pay all the debts or in the other hand. According to Hery (2015), it is a ratio used to measure the extent to which the company's assets are financed with debt. Put differently, it is used to measure how much debt the company must bear in order to fulfill its assets.

There are several types of solvency ratio that can be calculated for firm debt performance, namely: Debt-to-Total Asset ratio, Debt-to-Equity ratio, long term Debt to Equity ratio, Tangible Assets Debt coverage, Current Liabilities to Net worth, Times interest Coverage and Fixed charge Coverage (Periansya, 2015)

Leverage

Leverage is not merely the extent of debt within the capital structure of a firm but consists of both financial and operating leverage otherwise known as combined leverage (Mohohlo & Halif, 2018). Financial leverage refers to how much debt a company has used to finance their asset. Pandy (2009) Opinion that financial leverage is the use of the fixed-charge source of funds such as debt and preference capital along with the owners' equity in the capital structure of a firm. It is employed by a firm when it intends to earn more return on the fixed-charge fund than their costs. It is a financial technique that uses borrowed funds or preferred stock (items not involving fixed financial cost) to improve the return on an equity investment. It is concerned with the relationship between the firm's earnings available to common stock holders or the owners. Financial leverage is often referred to as trading on the "equity" (Akintola & Cole, 2020)

Operating Leverage on the other hand is defined as the extent of the use of fixed cost in the operation of the firm. A firm with a high degree of operating leverage also has higher break-even point since it must make sufficient contribution to cover fixed cost before there can be any profit (Olowe, 2017). Olowe further state that operating leverage has implication for the financial manager by stating that a highly operating leverage firm will

have its profit increasing at a high rate with a small increase in sales. On the other hand, for a highly operating leverage firm, a small drop in sales may wipe out profits and losses reported.

Operating and Financial leverage can be combined to show the total leverage effect for a given change in sales on earnings available to ordinary shareholders. Combined leverage combines the effect of business and financial risk (Olowo, 2017). They together cause wide fluctuation in earnings per share (EPS) for a given changes in sales and operating costs (Saleem, Rahman & Sultena, 2012). The operating leverage affects Earnings before Interest and Tax (EBIT) and financial leverage affects Earnings per Share (EPS), Return on Equity (ROE) and Return on Investment (ROI). (Saleem et al, 2012).

Financial Leverage is calculated by Debt ratio measured by the ratio of total debt to total assets. Total debt contains short- and long-term loan or financing from financial institutions, debenture/bonds, deferred payment arrangements for buying capital equipment, interest bearing public deposits, and any other interest-bearing loans. (Mohamad, Mohd, Amirul & Sharifah, 2020, Alaghi, 2013, Hooy & Lee, 2010, Igbal & Shah, 2010). The study will measure Financial Leverage as Debt Ratio.

Interest Coverage Ratio

Interest Coverage ratio is one of the most important ratios that need to be learned when assessing risk management and possible reduction methods. Interest coverage ratio plays a very important role for stakeholders and investors as it measures the ability of a business to pay interest on its outstanding debts. It acts as a solvency check for the business organization using financial advisors' business analysts for the investor to determine the ability of a business or a pay off the accumulated interest on the debts they are holding. Interest coverage ratio is also known as debt service coverage ratio or debt service ratio. It is determined by dividing the earnings before interest and taxes (EBIT) with the interest expenses payable by the company during the same period. It is in other words, the interest coverage ratio that measures the number of times a company is able to make payments on its existing debt with the EBIT or earnings before interest and taxes. It is also known as the Time Interest Earned Ratio.

Determining the ratio helps the lenders, investors, stockholders and debenture holders with data on how efficiently the business or the company is able to make payment for interest due on the long-term borrowings of the business. An interest coverage ratio of 1.5 is considered as healthy for a business. In general, a higher interest coverage ratio means that a company is earning sufficient money in order to pay off the interest due on long-term loans, which indicates that there is a very less chance of a financial default. Similarly, a low interest coverage ratio indicates a high debt burden on the company which increases the chance of bankruptcy. In such case, banks could hesitate to provide credit to the business.

Creditors and investors use this computation to understand the profitability and risk of a company. For instance, an investor is mainly concerned about seeing his investment in the company increase in value. A large part of this appreciation is based on profit and operational efficiencies. Thus, investors want to see that their company can pay its bills on time without having to sacrifice its operations and profits. A creditor on the other hand uses the interest coverage ratio to identify whether a company is able to support additional debt. If a company can't

afford to pay the interest on its debt, it certainly won't be able to afford to pay the principal payments. Thus, creditors use this formula to calculate the risk involved in lending.

Analyzing a coverage ratio can be tricky because it depends largely on how much risky the creditor or investor is willing to take depending on the desired risk limits. Many companies face the challenge of covering interest liabilities continuously. It is essential for solvency and liquidity to secure these liabilities with a relevant stream.

Total Debt Ratio

A firm can finance its operations with either debt or equity. If a firm finances its operation with debt, it is borrowing money from a lender for a certain period of time with a promise to pay the money back. In return, the lender received interest payments on the loan. The leverage a firm takes is measured by leverage ratio or debt ratio. Firms use the ratios to monitor their leverage and to make sure that they are at a satisfactory level. In so doing, one of the most common ratios used is the total debt ratio or the long-term debt ratio.

Firms within different industries have different target ratios that they strive to achieve and keep. Industries with tangible assets tend to have higher debt-ratios, as they can use their assets as collateral for loans whereas industries that have intangible assets usually have less debt since they do not have any collateral that can be used in case of a default (Brealey, Myers & Allen, 2011). There are different types of debt a firm can issue and different debt instruments to choose from. A broad separation is made between market debt (issue to the public) and non-market debt (bank loans). The most common ways of debt financing are borrowing money (bank loan or other loans), issuing bonds, preferred stock, collateralized debt obligations (CDOs), commercial papers or banker's acceptances. Debt could be attained in many different ways and another common way of categorizing debt is based on its different maturity. There is short-term debt, long-term debt and convertible debt.

Short-term debt is defined as payments due within one year and is found under liabilities on the financial position. This could be short term, bank loans, but also longer-term loans that are due within one year, as well as other outstanding debt maturing within a year. This account is very important and bankruptcy, for the firm, as it will affect the choice of capital structure.

Long-term debt is defined as any debt obligations that is not due within one year and is filed under non-current liabilities on the financial position. This also includes any possible leases the firm has. Convertible debts are a very special form of debt that means the outstanding debt has an option of becoming converted into common shares of the firm. Convertible bond that states in its bond indenture (contract) when, for how much and into how many share the bond can be converted.

Debt to Asset Ratio

The debt to asset ratio is a financial metric used to help understand the degree to which a company's operations are funded by debt. It is one of many leverage ratios that may be used to understand a company's capital structure. The debt to asset ratio is calculated by using a company's funded debt, sometimes called interest bearing liabilities. This refers to actual credit provided by direct lenders for which there are interest obligations (like bonds, short term loans from a commercial bank or subordinated debt), the ratio does not include total

liabilities (like accounts payable, etc). A company with a higher proportion of debt as a funding source is said to have high leverage while a lower proportion of debt as a funding source is said to have low leverage of all the leverage ratios used by the analyst to understand the financial position of a company debt to assets tends to be one of the less common ones. It represents the proportion (or the percentage of) asset that are financed by interest bearing liabilities as opposed to being funded by suppliers or shareholders. As a result, it is slightly more popular with lenders, who are less likely to extend additional credit to a borrower with very high debt to asset ratio. A valid critique of this ratio is that, the proportion of assets financed by non-financial liabilities is not considered. The ratio does not capture the company's entire set of cash "obligations" that are owed to external shareholders but captures only funded debt.

Important considerations about the Debt to Asset Ratio

There is no perfect score or ideal debt to asset ratio. As with all financial metrics, a "good ratio" is dependent upon many factors including the nature of the industry, the company's lifecycle stage and management preference, among others. A ratio approaching 1 (or 100%) is an extra-ordinarily high proportion of debt financing. This would be unsustainable over long periods of time as the firm would likely face solvency issues and risk triggering an event of default.

A debt to assets ratio that is too low can also be problematic. While unlikely to cause solvency issues, it could indicate poor capital structure decisions by management, resulting in a suboptimal return on equity for the firm's shareholders. The ratio is only useful in comparing businesses within the same industry as the capital structures of different industries. For example, for industries where there is a large proportion of tangible assets (inventory, equipment and commercial real estate), the book value of intangible assets may be minimal. Intuitively, such companies cannot be compared to other companies in industries that have a comparable funded debt to asset ratio, but where the assets are mostly held in intangible forms (goodwill, trademarks, patents, etc.)

Debt to Equity Ratio

The Debt-to-Equity ratio (also called gearing) is a leverage ratio that calculates the weight of total debt and financial liabilities against total shareholders' equity. It is a simple formula to show how capital has been raised to run a business. It is considered an important financial metric because of its ability to raise additional capital to investors; it is used to indicate how risky it is to invest in a company. A good debt to equity ratio is around 1 to 1.5. However, the ideal debt to equity ratio will vary depending on the industry because some industries use more debt financing than others. Capital-intensive industries like the financial and manufacturing industries often have higher ratios that can be greater than 2. A high debt to equity ratio indicates a business uses debt to finance its growth. Companies that invest large amounts of money in assets and operations (capital intensive company) often have a higher debt to equity ratio. To lenders and investors, a high ratio means a riskier investment because the business might not be able to produce enough money to repay its debts. If a debt-to-equity ratio is lower or closer to zero, it means that the business hasn't relied on borrowing to finance operations. Businesses with good debt to equity ratios are those that fall within the standard range for their industries. These companies are likely in a period of positive growth supported by balanced financing from both

debt lenders and equity shareholders. Although a company with good debt to equity ratio may look good on paper financially, it is worthy to note that this fiscal metric does not tell the entire story of how a business is using capital as a tool to scale. The business should not get too comfortable but instead turn attention to long-term debt to equity ratio as this has an impact on business financial health.

The Scenario of a Negative Debt to Equity Ratio

A negative debt to equity ratio occurs when a company has interest rates on its debts that are greater than the return on investment. Negative debt to equity ratio can also be a result of a company that has a negative net worth. Companies that experience a negative debt to equity ratio may be seen as risky to analysts, lenders and investors because this debt is a sign of financial instability.

A company can experience a negative debt to equity ratio for a number of reasons, including:

- Taking on additional debt to cover losses instead of issuing shareholder equity
- Expensing intangible assets, such as trademarks, that exceed pre-existing shareholder equity value
- Making large dividend payments that exceed shareholder's equity
- Experiencing financial loss in periods following large dividend payment

When any of these situations occur, they could signal a sign of financial distress of shareholders, investors and creditors.

Long-Term Debt to Equity Ratio

The long-term debt to equity ratio shows how much of a business assets are financial by long-term financial obligations, such as loans. To calculate long-term debt to equity ratio, divide long-term debt by shareholders' equity (Adam, 2023).

Profitability

Profitability is the independent variable in this study and is used as a proxy for systematic risk determinant. Profit defers from profitability (Zhiyao, Jarrad & Avraham, 2017). Profit is the main motive of every business organization. It ensures that the business continues as a going concern.

Profit maximization is a very crucial objective for a firm to remain in business and to withstand competition from firms operating in similar industry. It is a major pre-requisite for long-term survival of a firm, success of a firm and precondition for the achievement of other financial goals of a business entity (Gitman & Zutter, 2012, in Odusanya, Yinusa & Ilo, 2018). Profitability on the other hand is the business ability to generate earnings and compared to its expenses and other relevant costs incurred during a specific period of time (Umobong, 2015). Abdussalam (2006) opined that profitability is the ability to make profit from all the business ventures of an organization; it measures management efficiency in the use of organizational resources and in making changes to the business.

It stands as the overall objective of a business, to earn a satisfactory return on the funds invested in it while maintaining a sound financial position. It is a core measure of the performance of a firm and constitutes an

essential aspect of its financial reporting. Profitability reveals the firm ability and capacity to generate earnings at a rate of sales, level of assets and stock of capital in a specific period of time (Mergaretha & Supartika, 2016) Profitability ratios can be classified into Return on capital Employed (ROCE), Return on Asset (ROA), Return on Total Assets (ROTA), Return on Equity (ROE), and Return on Sales with the variant of Net Profit Percentage or Gross Profit Percentage. These ratios are used to assess the level of profitability of a firm. It is well by investor in combination with investment ratios to take investment decision (Orijinta & Okpalaukeje, 2018).

Pecking Order Theory

The study is anchored on Pecking Order Theory. According to Myers (1984) the pecking order theory was first introduced in 1961 by Donaldson, but was later altered and modified by Myers and Maljuf in 1984. The theory regards what type of financing a firm prefers when it is in need of more funding, whether it is internal or external. According to the theory, firms prefer internal funding, that is internally generated funds, rather than external funding. If internal funding cannot be extracted and external funding has to be used, the firm will prefer to issue debt rather than equity (Myers, 1984). The reasons why firms have that order of preference have to do with *asymmetric information*. Asymmetric information occurs because managers have more information than the shareholders about the state of the firm and how well it is doing. The result is therefore that the shareholders will base their belief on the firm's future on the manager's actions. The manager's actions are believed to signal information about the state of the firm. Issuing shares sends a message that the shares are overvalued, whereas issuing debt does not send any message. Debt issuing is therefore favored over equity issuing (Brealey et al., 2011).

Empirical Review

Wang (2002) study on liquidity management, operating performance and corporate value in Japan and Taiwan found that negative relationship exists between cash conversion cycle and return on asset, and return on equity. The findings indicated that aggressive liquidity management enhances operating performance and is associated with higher corporate values in both countries in spite of differences in structural characteristics or in financial system of a firm.

Nwude, Okpara, Agbadua & Udeh (2016) examined the impact of debt structure on firm performance: empirical evidence from Nigerian quoted firms using 12 years annual panel data spanning from 2001 to 2012 and analyzed using fixed and random effect regression analysis. The finds shows that debt structure has negative and significant impact on the performance of Nigerian quoted firms and concludes that debt structure contribute negatively to the performance of Nigerian quoted firms.

Alam, Ali, Rehman, & Akam (2011) examined the impact of working capital management on profitability and market value of Pakistani firms. Data for the study were source from sixty-five listed companies in Karachi stock exchange between five years 2005 to 2009. Data analyzed using correlation and multiple regression technique of spss found that significant relationship exist between cash conversion cycle, current ratio, current

assets to total asset ratio and debt to asset ratio, working capital component with market value and firm's profitability.

Anup & Suman (2010) examined the impact of capital structure on firm's value: evidence from Bangladesh. The study was on seventy-seven firms from four dominant sectors of Bangladesh capital market (Pharmaceuticals and chemicals, Fuel and Power, Food and Engineering industries. While share price stood as the proxy for firm value firm size, profitability, public ownership, dividend payout, asset and operating leverage, growth rate, EPS, long term debt to total asset and current ratio stood for capital structure. Descriptive, correlation and regression analysis results found that EPS, dividend payout ratio, long term debt to total assets and current ratio have positive coefficient while public ownership, operating leverage, sales growth have negative coefficient on firm value. Summarily, the study reviewed that capital structure has impact on the firm value of sample Bangladesh firms.

Albert, Michael & Daniel (2013) examined the effect of capital structure on profitability of listed firms in the Ghana during the years 2005 to 2009. While

Short-term debt, long term debt and total debt stood as the proxy for capital structure, return on asset stood for profitability. Findings from the analysis of data source from the Ghanian stock exchange' 2010 fact book revealed that short- term debt has significant positive relationship with profitability while long term debt and total debt have significant negative relationship with profitability.

Mouamer 2011 examined the determinants of capital structure of Palestine listed companies over a five-year period 2000-2004 using profitability, leverage ratio (total debt, short-term debt, and long-term debt), liquidity, age as the proxy for capital structure while firm size and sales growth serves as control variables. Data analyzed using ANOVA shows that total debt has positive and significant effect on firm Tangibility, while long term debt and short-term debt has insignificant relationship with firm tangibility.

Abor, Kumankoma, Fiawoyife & Osei (2009) examined risk exposure and financial policy: An empirical analysis of 34 emerging markets over the period from 1990 to 2006 using profitability, dividend, asset tangibility, growth opportunities, and GDP per capital as the determinants of the financial policy of emerging market firms were analyzed with correlation and regression analysis. The study found that firms with high profitability of survival are likely to employ more debt. The level of business risk exposure is important in influencing the financial decision of firms in emerging market economies.

Bokpin, Aboagye & Osei (2010) examined risk exposure and corporate financial policy of listed firms in the Ghanian stock exchange from 2002 to 2007. The study found that the impact of risk exposure depends on capital structure (financial leverage and debt ratio), capital structure is adjusted differently in response to different kinds of risk exposure (cooperate risk, bankruptcy risk), firm size and profitability are found to be significant driving factors in shaping corporate financial policy of the GSE.

Rocca 2007 examined the influence of corporate governance on the relation between capital structure and value. The descriptive model study found that capital structure represents one of the many instruments that can preserve corporate governance efficiency and protects its ability to create value.

Balcilar, Karadeniz, Kandir & Onal (2009) examined the determinants of capital structure: evidence from Turkish lodging companies. Data source from fifteen Turkish lodging firms between the periods of 1994 to 2006 and analyzed using fixed effect panel regression analysis found that effective tax rates, tangibility of assets and return on asset relates negatively with significant parameter estimates of debt ratio while free cash flow, non-debt tax shields, growth opportunities, net commercial credit position and firm size have insignificant parameter estimates and do not relate to debt ratio of lodging companies in Turkey.

Alwalid M.S (2020) examined the effect of capital structure on profitability of Basic material of Saudi Arabia Firms during the period 2009 to 2018 using regression analysis, fixed model and random effect model. The findings shows that negative relationship exist between short term debt to total asset ratio, long term debt and profitability while positive relationship exist between total debt and profitability.

Ebaid (2009) examined the impact of capital structure choice on firm performance: empirical evidence from Egypt between the period 1997 to 2005 using thee accounting measures of financial performance return on equity, return on assets and gross profit margin. Data were source from non-financial Egyptian listed firms and the findings the analysis shown that capital structure choice decision in general term has a weak-to-no-impact on firms' performance.

Ezeoha (2008) studied on the firm size and corporate leverage choice in a developing economy: evidence from Nigeria. Data generated from financial reports of the listed firms between 1990 to 2006 were analyze using regression analysis. The finding from fixed effect panel regression shows that firm size is negatively and significantly relates to financial leverage

Joshua & Nicholas (2009) examined on how we explain the capital structure of SMEs in sub-Saharan African. Long-term debt and short-term debt ratio stood for capital structure while firm's age, size, asset structure, profitability, and growth stood for firm level characteristics. Finding from the regression model shown that firm level characteristics affect the capital structure of Ghanaian SMEs.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The research design that was adopted for this study is the ex-post facto research design because, it sought to investigate the effect of independent variables on the dependent variables after occurrence using existing data from secondary source which cannot be manipulated. The ex-post facto research design is causal comparative research which is used when the researcher intends to determine cause-effect relationship between the independent and dependent variable with a view to establishing a causal link between them (Ofor 2022). Therefore, this study sought to ascertain the effect of solvency ratio on the financial performance of listed industrial firms in Nigeria Exchange Group. The population for this study included all the industrial goods firms quoted on the Nigerian Exchange Group for the year 2013 to 2023. There were 13 quoted industrial goods firms on the Nigeria Stock Exchange in December, 2023 (Nigeria Exchange Group). This study adopted secondary

data and the data were sourced from the annual reports and accounts of the various industrial goods firms quoted on the Nigeria stock Exchange from 2013 to 2023, a period of (11) year. The information relating to the components of solvency ratio (Interest Coverage Ratio, Debt-to-Assets Ratios, and Debt-to-Equity Ratio) and financial performance (Return on Asset) were analyzed through descriptive statistics, and random effect regression analysis. The liner regression model used in this study was adopted from the prior studies of Umenzekwe, P., C, Okonewa, O., & Uche, C., G. (2022). The model is consistent with the previous studies in pattern, but peculiar in content with this study and was guided by the Fixed Effect Regression analysis because the study was based on panel data. Secondly, the Fixed and Random Effect Regression model took care of heteroskedasticity from the respective data of variables.

The adopted model is as thus stated:

$$Y = F (X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4, X_5 \dots) \dots\dots\dots 1$$

$$ROA = F (ICR, DTAR, DTER,) \dots\dots\dots 2$$

The linear model for this study was adopted from the linear models of Umenzekwe, P., C, Okonewa, O., & Uche, C., G. (2022).

Based on the variable introduced, we specify the following regression equation

$$LNROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LNICR_{it} + \beta_2 LNDTAR_{it} + \beta_3 LNDTER_{it} + \mu \dots\dots 3$$

Where;

LNROA denotes LOG RETURN ON ASSET

LNICR= LOG INTEREST COVERAGE RATIO

LNDTAR= LOG DEBT TO ASSET RATIO

LNDTER= LOG DEBT TO EQUITY RATIO

i denotes number of firms

t denotes years or time series dimensions ranging from 2013 to 2023

\sum is the error term of the model

$\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5$ ----- is the regression model coefficients.

4.0 ANALYSIS AND INTERPRESENTATION

Descriptive Analysis

Table 1: Analysis of the Descriptive Statistics of solvency ratio and financial performance

	LNROA	LNICR	LNDTAR	LNDTER
Mean	-2.780997	1.759067	-1.093699	-0.520024
Median	-2.441913	1.854251	-0.945470	-0.439295
Maximum	-0.446287	7.982925	1.383290	1.656512
Minimum	-6.907755	-2.488915	-4.422849	-4.961845
Std. Dev.	1.315091	2.092866	0.847073	1.127913
Skewness	-0.679790	-0.032831	-1.486030	-1.204832
Kurtosis	3.168441	3.574397	6.668703	5.612951
Jarque-Bera Probability	7.038105 0.029628	1.253413 0.534349	83.59695 0.000000	47.37747 0.000000
Sum	-250.2897	158.3160	-98.43295	-46.80217

Sum Sq. Dev.	153.9222	389.8278	63.86045	113.2246
Observations	99	99	99	99

Source: Researcher computed result

The result on Table 1 demonstrates the descriptive statistics of solvency ratio and three independent variables for 9 listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria for 11 years period of 2013 to 2023. The result mean value for return on asset is 2.78. This indicates that return on asset on average of the sample industrial goods firms in Nigeria is negatively 2.78%. This implies that averagely, the listed industrial goods firms’ return on the asset that was employed in operation is 2.78%. It further indicates that the average rate of return on investment is has down by 2.78%. This value connotes low performance from asset utilisation of industrial goods firms in their business operations in Nigeria with standard deviation of ±1.31. Interest Coverage ratio has average score of 1.75 with standard deviation of ±2.09. This indicates that the listed industrial goods firms’ earnings in Nigeria cover its current interest payment by 1.75 times. Debt-to-assets ratio has mean value of 1.09 with standard deviation of ±1.12. This indicates that on average, 1.09% of the industrial goods firms’ assets are funded by debt. Debt-to-equity ratio has mean value of 0.52% with standard deviation of ±1.12 This indicate that on average, industrial goods firms’ debts are covered by 052% equity.

The normality of the values can be measured with skewness, kurtosis or Jarque Bera (JB) statistics. Using the Jarque-Bera, the p-value among the variable are as follows; return on asset (0.02), interest coverage ratio (0.53), debt-to-asset ratio (0.00), and debt-to-equity ratio (0.00).

Normality Graph

The joint probability of the Jarque-Bera as presented in the normality graph above shows that the data for the variables of the study is normally distributed at 0.48% above the significant valve of 5% and kurtosis 3.07. This indicates that outlier variable does not exist and the variable is reliable for drawing generalization sample of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria Exchange Group.

Models Estimation

The model estimation was done using the panel regression techniques. The Fixed Effect Model and Random Effect Model were conducted and then Hausman test was employed to determine the most suitable for the interpretation of result. The result of the Hausman is shown on Table 2.

Table 2

Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test

Equation: Untitled

Test cross-section random effects

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	18.515724	3	0.0003

Hausman Effect Test

The Hausman test in Table 3 above was to determine the most appropriate technique between the fixed and random model to analyse the study. The test result is; statistic value = 18.515724 and probability value = 0.0003. Therefore, since the p. value 0.0003 is less than 0.05% significant level, the study accepts the alternative hypothesis which states that the fixed effect model is preferred for the analysis of the study.

Regression

Dependent Variable: LNROA

Method: Panel Least Squares

Date: 12/03/24 Time: 15:38

Sample: 2013 2023

Periods included: 11

Cross-sections included: 9

Total panel (balanced) observations: 99

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-3.572749	0.290853	-12.28370	0.0000
LNICR	-0.012048	0.056711	-0.212439	0.8323
LNDTAR	-0.767509	0.276431	-2.776496	0.0069
LNDTER	0.050919	0.213925	0.238023	0.8125

Effects Specification

Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)

R-squared	0.550389	Mean dependent var	-2.780997
Adjusted R-squared	0.486982	S.D. dependent var	1.315091
S.E. of regression	0.941937	Akaike info criterion	2.841809
Sum squared resid	69.20516	Schwarz criterion	3.175117

Log likelihood	-115.8814	Hannan-Quinn criter.	2.976219
F-statistic	8.680292	Durbin-Watson stat	2.241567
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

Source: researcher computation E view 9 Results

The analysis is therefore based on Fixed Effect Model to interpret the places of interest coverage ratio, debt-to-asset ratio and debt-to-equity ratio in industry sector firms in Nigeria.

The result of the coefficient of determination (R-square) is 0.55. This means that the explanatory variables (interest coverage ratio, debt-to-asset ratio, debt-to-equity ratio) explain the respondent variable (return on asset) of industrial goods firm in Nigeria Exchange Group up to about 55%.

The F-statistics is used to test the overall effect of the model. The F-statistics is 8.680292 with a P-value of 0.0000. Since the P-value is less than 0.05% level of significance, the study concludes that explanatory variable including (interest coverage ratio, debt-to-asset ratio, debt-to-equity ratio) accounted for about 55% of the return on asset in industrial goods firms in Nigeria Exchange Group.

The result of the coefficient of independent variable is used to produce equation of the relationship from the model as given below:

$$ROA = -0.012048ICR + -0.767509DTAR + 0.050919DTER + -3.572749$$

Return on Asset and Interest Coverage Ratio

The coefficient of the regression for interest coverage ratio is -0.012. This means that interest coverage ratio (ICR) which is a proxy for Solvency ratio, has negative relationship with return on asset. This means that a unit increase in interest coverage payment reduces return on asset by 1%.

Return on Asset and Debt to asset ratio

The coefficient of the regression for Debt to asset ratio is -0.76. This indicates that debt to asset reduces 0.76 times for a single increase in the return on asset of industrial goods firms Nigeria Exchange Group.

Return on Asset and Debt to equity ratio

The result of the coefficient of the regression for debt-to-equity ratio 0.05. This shows a positive relationship between return on asset and debt to equity ratio of industrial goods firms. This implies that a unit rise in the value of equity coverage to debt will increase the return on asset of industrial goods firms by 50%.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis One

Interest coverage ratio has no significant effect on the Return on Asset of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria Exchange Group.

The t-statistic for ICR is -0.2124. The probability value is 0.8323 which is greater than 0.05% level of significance. The decision rule is to reject the null hypothesis when the P-value is less than 0.05% level of significance, or to accept on the otherwise. Since the P-value (0.83) is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, the study did not reject the null hypothesis that "Interest coverage ratio has no significant effect with the return on asset of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria Exchange Group. The study thus concludes that interest coverage ratio has a negative and insignificant effect on the return on asset of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria Exchange Group.

Hypothesis Two

Debt on asset ratio has no significant effect on the Return on Asset of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria Exchange Group.

The result shows that the t-statistic for DTAR is -2.7764. The probability value is 0.006 which is less than 0.05% level of significance. The decision rule is to reject the null hypothesis when the P-value is less than 0.05% level of significance, or to accept on the otherwise. Since the P-value is less than the 0.05% level of significance, the study rejects the null hypothesis that “Debt to Asset Ratio has no significant effect on the Return on Asset of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria Exchange Group”. The study then posits that Debt to Asset Ratio has significant effect on the Return on Asset of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria Exchange Group.

Hypothesis Three

Debt to Equity Ratio has no significant effect on the return on Asset listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria Exchange Group.

The result shows that the t-statistic for DTER is -0.2380. The probability value 0.8125 is greater than 0.05% level of significance. The decision rule is to reject the null hypothesis when the P-value is less than 0.05% level of significance and accept otherwise. Since the P-value (0.8125) is greater than the 0.05% level of significance, the study did not reject the null hypothesis that “Debt to Equity Ratio has no significant effect on the Return on Asset of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria Exchange Group”. The study however, posits that debt on equity ratio has no significant effect on the return on asset of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria Exchange Group.

5.0 SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings

The study has investigated the effect of solvency ratio on the return of asset of the performance of industrial goods firms in Nigeria Exchange Group. The explanatory variables of solvency ratio are interest coverage ratio, debt to asset ratio, and debt to equity ratio. The data were gathered from the annual report and statement of accounts of 9 selected industrial goods firms in Nigeria Exchange Group for a period of 11 years consisting 99 observations. The panel regression technique based on fixed effect model was adopted for the analysis. The results are summarized as follows:

1. Interest coverage ratio has negative relationship and statistically, insignificant effect on the return on asset of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria Exchange Group.
2. Debt to asset ratio has negative relationship and statistically, significant effect on the return on asset of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria Exchange Group.
3. Debt to equity ratio has positive relationship and statistically, insignificant effect on the return on asset of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria Exchange Group.

Conclusion

Most essential purpose of a company is to amplify its returns for investors. The return can be maximized by reducing the portion of risk. Complete understanding of these factors is very fruitful for investors and financial policy makers. The explanatory variable of the study explained only 55% of variations in return on asset, which means that there are other factors outside the explanatory variables of this study which contributes to the effect solvency ratio of listed industrial good firms in Nigeria Exchange Group.

The study concludes that debt to asset ratio is the only significant variable on return on asset of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria Exchange Group. Although interest coverage ratio and debt to equity ratio financial maintain negative and positive coefficients respectively with insignificant effect on the return on asset of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria Exchange Group. It further provides opportunity for regulators and managers to better understand the dynamics of financial management theories and practices of the market that improves the wealth creation of the investors and as well, sustains the performance of industrial goods firms in Nigeria Exchange Group. Secondly, as every corporate organization is concerned on how to lessen investment risk and increase their performance favorably, this study is an eye opener to the management of industrial goods firms in Nigeria Exchange Group.

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings and conclusions of the study, we recommend among others that

1. Managers should endeavor to improve on the overall solvency ratio metric strategies that would enhance enterprise's ability to meet its long-term debt obligation.
2. Managers are encouraged to finance its operations more through equity in the proportion that it could cover its debt since debt-to-equity ratio has a positive coefficient relationship with return on asset. This variably means that an increase to debt-to-equity ratio increases the return on assets of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria Exchange Group.
3. Managers of industrial goods firms in Nigeria should proficiently strategize the interest coverage ratio of the firms, in a manner that the Operational efficiency of the firm takes comparative advantage over the exposure of investment risk.

REFERENCES

- Abdussalam, M. A. (2006). An empirical study of firm structuring and profitability relationship: The case of Jordan. *Journal of Economic and Administrative Sciences*, 22(1), 41-59.
- Abor, J. Y., Kumankoma, E. S., Fiawouite, E. U., & Osei, K. A. (2009). Risk exposure and financial policy: An empirical analysis of emerging markets. *Journal of Economic Studies*, 36, 195-211.
- Abor, J. (2007). Debt policy and performance of SMEs: Evidence from Ghanaian and South African firms. *The Journal of Risk Finance*, 8(4), 364-379.

- Afeef, M. (2011). Analyzing the impact of working capital management on the profitability of SMEs in Pakistan. *International Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 2(22).
- Akintola, A. F., & Cole, A. A. (2020). Impact of combined leverage on capital employed of selected listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. *IOSR Journal of Economics and Finance*, 11(3), 51-56.
- Alaghi, K. (2013). Determinants of systematic risk of the listed companies in Tehran Stock Exchange. *Journal of Basic and Applied Scientific Research*, 3(1), 596-600.
- Albert, A. A., Michael, N. B., & Daniel, H. (2013). The effect of capital structure on profitability of listed firms in Ghana. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 5(31), 215-229.
- Alwalid, M. S. (2020). The effect of capital structure on profitability of basic materials in Saudi Arabia firms. *Journal of Mathematical Finance*, 10(4).
- Allam, A., Ali, A., Akram, M., & Rehman, S. (2011). Impact of working capital management on profitability and market valuation of Pakistani firms. *European Journal of Economics, Finance and Administrative Sciences*.
- Anup, C., & Suman, P. (2010). Impact of capital structure on firm's value: Evidence from Bangladesh. *Business and Economic Horizons*, 3(3).
- Aziz, S., & Abbas, U. (2019). Effect of debt financing on firm performance: A study on the nonfinancial sector of Pakistan. *Open Journal of Economics and Commerce*, 2(1), 8-15.
- Balcilar, M., Karadeniz, E., Kandir, Y., & Onal, Y. B. (2009). Determinants of capital structure: Evidence from Turkish lodging companies. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 21(5), 595-609.
- Bokpin, G. A., Aboagye, A., & Osei, K. A. (2010). Risk exposure and corporate financial policy on the Ghanaian stock exchange. *Journal of Risk Finance*, 11(3), 323-332.
- Ebaid, I. (2009). The impact of capital structure choice on firm performance: Empirical evidence from Egypt. *Journal of Risk Finance*, 10(5), 477-487.
- Ezeoha, A. E. (2008). Firm size and corporate financial leverage choice in a developing economy: Evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of Risk Finance*, 9(4), 351-364.

- Frazier, P., Jiang, B., & Prater, E. (2006). Outsourcing effects on firms' operations performance: An empirical study. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 26(12), 1280-1300.
- Gitman, I., & Zutter, C. (2012). *Principios de administración financiera*. Pearson Educación.
- Hadi, A. (2006). Review of capital market efficiency: Some evidence from Jordanian market. *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*.
- Hooy, C. W., & Lee, K. Y. (2010). The determinants of systematic risk exposures of the airline industry in East Asia. *World Applied Sciences Journal*, 10(1), 91-98.
- Idowu, A., Lawrencina, A., & Ogunpide, O. (2012). Working capital management, firms performance, and market valuation in Nigeria. *International Journal of Social and Human Sciences*.
- Igbai, M. J., & Shah, S. Z. (2010). Determinants of systematic risk. *Journal of Commerce*, 4(1), 47-56.
- Jensen, M. C. (1984). Agency costs of free cash flow, corporate finance, and takeovers. *American Economic Review*, 78, 323-329.
- Joshua, A., & Nicholas, B. (2009). How do we explain the capital structure of SMEs in sub-Saharan Africa? *Journal of Economic Studies*, 36(1), 83-97.
- Margaretha, F., & Supartika, N. (2016). Factors affecting profitability of small-medium enterprises (SMEs) firms listed in Indonesian Stock Exchange. *Journal of Economic Business and Management*, 4(2), 132-137.
- Mohohlo, M., & Halif, F. (2018). The impact of operating leverage on the capital structure of exchange-listed firms before and after the 2008 global financial cases. *Journal of Economic and Financial Science*, 11(1), 1-10.
- Mohamad, N. J., Mohd, F. B., Amirul, A. M., & Sharifah, F. S. (2020). Determinants of systematic risk: Empirical evidence from Shariah-compliant firms listed on Bursa Malaysia.
- Myers, S. C. (1984). The capital structure puzzle. *Journal of Finance*, 39(3), 575-592.
- Mouamer, F. A. (2011). The determinants of capital structure of Palestine-listed companies. *The Journal of Risk Finance*, 12(3), 226-241.

- Nwadiolor, E. O., Akaji, O., & Agubata, N. (2021). Effect of debt-equity financing on firms performance in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Financial Management*, 7(3), 73-82.
- Nosa, I., & Ose, S. (2010). Capital structure and corporate performance in Nigeria: An empirical investigation. *AAU JMS*, 1(1).
- Oboro, O. G., & Samuel, A. P. (2021). Capital structure optimality and performance metrics of selected multinationals in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Innovation Research*, 9(1), 66-80.
- Ofor, N. K. (2022). *A basic text in research writing for tertiary institutions*. Eternal Press.
- Olowo, R. A. (2017). *Financial management: Concepts, financial system, and business finance*. University Press.
- Ongore, V. O. (2011). The relationship between ownership structure and firm performance: An empirical analysis of listed companies in Kenya. *African Journal of Business Management*, 5(6), 2120-2128.
- Orjinta, H. I., & Okpalaukeje, R. U. (2018). Effect of cash cycle on profitability of basic material firms in Nigeria. *J. Bio. Innov.*, 7(1), 12-28.
- Pandy, I. M. (2009). *Financial management*. New Delhi, India.
- Saleem, Q., & Rehman, R. U. (2011). Impacts of liquidity ratios on profitability. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Research in Business*, 1, 95-98.
- Umobong, A. A. (2015). Assessing the impact of liquidity and profitability ratio on growth of profit in pharmaceutical firms in Nigeria. *European Journal of Accounting Auditing and Finance Research*, 3(10), 97-114.
- Wang, Y. J. (2002). Liquidity management, operating performance, and corporate value: Evidence from Japan and Taiwan. *Journal of Multinational Financial Management*, 12, 159-169.
- Zhang, X. (2011). Firm-level performance impact of IS support for product innovation. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 14(1), 118-132.
- Zhiyao, C., Jarrad, H., & Avraham, K. (2017). Operating leverage, profitability, and capital structure. 24th CFEA Kenan-Flagler Business School Cambridge UK.